

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain
interplaY

Deliverable 4.3

Learning models and spatio-temporal harmonization

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Research in HEREDITARY involves understanding properties, relationships, and patterns in large and complex heterogeneous data, to obtain knowledge from biomedical datasets. We aim to link different modalities together to discover novel correlations, biological pathways, and ultimately to stratify patients towards a personalized medicine approach.

Work Package 4 of the HEREDITARY project develops tools for harmonizing heterogeneous biomedical data before multimodal integration. The goal is to minimise biases introduced by acquisition instruments and subject variability that can impact downstream analysis.

Reporting on the progress of Tasks 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5, this deliverable aims to provide practical harmonization strategies and self-supervised learning models that improve the quality, fairness, and comparability of biomedical data. As biomedical datasets grow in size and diversity, differences in acquisition settings, preprocessing choices, and subject characteristics can introduce variability that affects downstream results. Addressing these issues early helps avoid misleading conclusions and supports more stable multimodal models.

The methods presented here address this need by providing clear and straightforward steps for harmonization across several key domains, including electroencephalography (EEG), optical coherence tomography (OCT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and genomic/transcriptomic data.

Results indicate that standardized, lightweight preprocessing often works well, and that subject-based evaluation prevents inflated performance. In terms of advanced learning, self-supervised methods show particular promise for learning generalizable representations in imaging modalities. MRI studies highlight the need for clearer reporting of acquisition parameters and resolution settings to ensure comparability. OCT datasets vary widely, but some are well-suited for harmonized analysis, and genomics SSL models are improving rapidly. Additionally, analysis of clinical data has been shown to reveal meaningful patient groups. Overall, simple and transparent workflows lead to more reliable results.

These methods help reduce unnecessary variability and support more consistent analyses, while also laying the groundwork for improved multimodal modeling and more reliable clinical insights.

The next phase will focus on integrating these harmonization approaches into a unified, multimodal pipeline that can be applied across partners. This includes refining preprocessing and evaluation steps, integrating self-supervised models into routine workflows, and validating the methods on additional datasets. Furthermore, we will leverage these harmonized datasets to support federated learning, ensuring that model quality remains high even when training across distributed sources.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ASR	Artifact Subspace Reconstruction
CV	Cross-validation
DL	Deep Learning
EEG	ElectroEncephaloGraphy
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
GAT	Graph Attention Network
GDM	General Distance Measure
GML	Graph Machine Learning
ICA	Independent Component Analysis
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
N-LOSO	Nested-Leave One Subject Out
N-LNSO	Nested-Leave N Subject Out
OCT	Optical Coherence Tomography
RSC	Repeated Spectral Clustering
SSL	Self-Supervised Learning
T-ResNet	Temporal ResNet
VAE	Variational AutoEncoder

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1 Introduction

1.1 Multimodal Data Integration and Harmonization Challenges

Modern biomedical research increasingly depends on integrating multiple data modalities to achieve a comprehensive understanding of disease mechanisms. Each modality contributes unique and complementary insights: for example, EEG captures neurophysiological activity with high temporal resolution, OCT and MRI reveal tissue structure and function, histopathology depicts cellular morphology, and omics data uncover molecular mechanisms ([Yoon et al., 2024](#)). Integrating these diverse sources enables the identification of complex correlations and biological pathways that single-modality analyses cannot capture ([Hao et al., 2025](#)).

Multimodal data integration faces major challenges due to heterogeneity in acquisition instruments, imaging protocols, and preprocessing pipelines, which introduce systematic biases, limit reproducibility across sites ([Nan et al., 2022](#)), and reduce the effectiveness of federated learning. Without proper harmonization, such inconsistencies can lead to spurious associations and poor model generalization across populations. To address these challenges, recent frameworks have emphasized the need for standardized evaluation metrics and checklists to assess bias, variance, and reproducibility in multimodal datasets ([Hao et al., 2025](#)).

Advances in fusion strategies — such as co-attention and cross-modal alignment — further improve interpretability and robustness by integrating histopathological, genomic, and clinical information for predictive modeling ([Lou et al., 2025](#)). Broader surveys in the field highlight the importance of interpretable, privacy-preserving AI architectures and standardized harmonization practices to ensure trustworthy clinical deployment ([Liu et al., 2025](#)). Collectively, these efforts demonstrate that effective multimodal integration in healthcare requires not only advanced modeling techniques but also rigorous harmonization standards to ensure scientific and clinical validity ([Schouten et al., 2025](#)).

1.2 Preprocessing and Deep Learning

Deep learning has reshaped biomedical data analysis by learning complex patterns directly from data, achieving notable success across multiple modalities such as medical imaging and genomics ([Shouten et al. 2025](#)). However, model performance remains highly dependent on data quality and preprocessing choices.

The interaction between preprocessing and deep learning is not straightforward. Traditional pipelines often apply extensive preprocessing steps optimized for statistical methods, which may not be ideal for deep learning models. Insufficient preprocessing can leave artifacts that degrade performance, whereas excessive processing may remove informative signals ([Li et al., 2023](#)). Identifying preprocessing strategies that balance artifact reduction and information preservation is therefore essential.

Beyond conventional preprocessing, self-supervised learning (SSL) provides a complementary, and in some occasions an alternative approach by learning representations from unlabeled data that are robust to technical variation ([Del Pup et al., 2023](#)). SSL has proven valuable in biomedical applications with limited labeled data

and has shown strong potential for improving representation quality and generalization across modalities ([Richter et al., 2025](#)).

In summary, effective integration of preprocessing and advanced learning paradigms such as SSL is key to developing reliable and generalizable deep learning models in biomedical research.

1.3 Grand Challenge

The [Grand Challenge](#) platform plays a strategic role as an open hub for developing, benchmarking, and sharing machine-learning solutions in biomedical imaging. Recognized as one of the largest platforms for exchanging benchmark datasets and AI models, it enables access to a wide range of harmonization and analysis algorithms across different imaging modalities. By integrating Grand Challenge into the federated HEREDITARY infrastructure, we can distribute, evaluate, and compare multimodal harmonization algorithms across sites while ensuring data privacy and standardization. This facilitates cross-site interoperability and supports the alignment of heterogeneous data sources such as imaging, histopathology, and genomics.

Although mainly existing tools have been deployed and no new algorithms have yet been developed specifically with HEREDITARY data, numerous existing solutions are already available through Grand Challenge, and additional, project-specific algorithms will be produced in later phases as the harmonization framework evolves.

1.4 Modality-Specific Considerations

Biomedical data modalities exhibit distinct sources of variability and artifacts, requiring tailored preprocessing strategies to ensure reliable deep learning performance. However, the degree to which traditional preprocessing remains necessary in the context of modern deep or self-supervised models is still being explored.

1.4.1 EEG

EEG recordings are prone to artifacts from eye blinks, muscle activity, and electrical interference. While SSL offers a robust solution by learning directly from noisy inputs ([Eldele et al., 2023](#)), it requires massive datasets to generalize effectively. Conventional preprocessing pipelines, however, create a bottleneck as they are often too computationally inefficient to handle data at this scale. Consequently, optimized high-throughput pipelines are being developed to accelerate artifact removal. These scalable approaches allow for the efficient processing of large-scale datasets, which is critical for stabilizing SSL training and enhancing downstream task performance ([Gjølbye et al., 2024](#)).

1.4.2 MRI and OCT

MRI and OCT data vary across scanners and protocols, introducing site-specific biases that challenge generalization. A vast array of image harmonization methodologies has emerged to mitigate these effects, with deep learning approaches like Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) driving substantial advancements ([Abbasi et al., 2024](#)). These frameworks improve consistency across heterogeneous datasets while preserving diagnostically relevant features ([Huang et al., 2023](#)).

1.4.3 Multi-Omics

Multi-omics datasets—spanning genomics, transcriptomics, epigenomics and proteomics—face challenges such as batch effects from sequencing platforms and library preparation protocols. These effects can obscure biological signals and confound model interpretation. Deep generative models, including variational autoencoders and contrastive learning frameworks, have been employed for batch correction and data integration, improving representation consistency across datasets ([Baião et al., 2025](#)). At the same time, scalability remains a challenge for genome-wide applications, and the tissue- and cell-type specificity of transcriptomic data further complicates harmonization ([Alharbi et al., 2022](#)). Addressing these issues is crucial for generalizable multi-omics deep learning pipelines.

2 EEG

Electroencephalography (EEG) provides a non-invasive, high-temporal-resolution window into brain activity, making it a key tool in neuroscience and clinical research. However, EEG data are inherently affected by high intra- and inter-subject variability, which arises from multiple sources — including anatomical differences, electrode positioning, acquisition hardware, experimental protocols, and environmental factors. This variability poses significant challenges for the generalization, reproducibility, and interpretability of data-driven and deep learning approaches.

In the context of the Hereditary project, understanding and mitigating this variability is crucial for developing robust multimodal and harmonized analytical pipelines. Addressing these issues requires complementary efforts spanning preprocessing, data harmonization, and self-supervised learning strategies.

To this end, three recent works performed within HEREDITARY that provide methodological and practical insights will be better described in this area:

1. *The more, the better? Evaluating the role of EEG preprocessing for deep learning applications* ([Del Pup et al., 2024](#)) explores how different preprocessing strategies influence DL model performance and interpretability.
2. *The role of data partitioning on the performance of EEG-based deep learning models in supervised cross-subject analysis: A preliminary study* ([Del Pup et al., 2025](#)) provides an analysis of data partitioning and cross-validation effect in DL, offering guidelines to prevent data leakage and inflated performance claims.
3. *SelfEEG: A Python library for Self-Supervised Learning in Electroencephalography* ([Del Pup et al., 2024](#)) proposes a unified library for representation learning from raw EEG, enabling models to generalize across subjects and acquisition settings.

Together, these studies contribute to a coherent strategy for EEG data harmonization and robust feature learning, providing a foundation for reproducible and scalable neurophysiological analyses.

2.1 Pre-processing

Electroencephalography (EEG) preprocessing is a critical yet highly debated initial step in the analysis pipeline, primarily due to the necessity to manage a wide array of physiological artifacts—such as those from eye blinks, eye movements, and muscle activity—that can severely distort the neural signal of interest and compromise the validity of downstream interpretations ([Jiang et al. 2025](#)). The core of the debate lies in a fundamental trade-off: while aggressive artifact removal can clean the data, it may also inadvertently remove or alter genuine neural activity, potentially introducing bias and leading to misleading conclusions ([Jas et al. 2025](#)). This dilemma is compounded by the lack of a single standardized method, leading to substantial variability in preprocessing practices across studies.

Within the HEREDITARY project, the report “The More, the Better? Evaluating the Role of EEG Preprocessing for Deep Learning Applications” developed and assessed

automated preprocessing pipelines for EEG harmonization. These pipelines aim to standardize and improve EEG data quality before multimodal integration with other biomedical signals, thus reducing variability across acquisition setups.

2.1.1 Objective

The primary objective of this study is to investigate how varying degrees of EEG preprocessing affect the performance and generalizability of deep learning (DL) models across both clinical and non-clinical applications. Despite decades of EEG research, there remains no consensus on the optimal preprocessing strategy for DL scenarios—ranging from raw input data to complex pipelines involving artifact correction techniques like Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR). This work aims to clarify whether complex pipelines truly enhance model accuracy or whether simpler, lightweight filtering approaches suffice for robust EEG harmonization.

2.1.2 Methods

Four automated preprocessing pipelines of increasing complexity were tested:

- Raw (no preprocessing)
- Filt (basic filtering and re-referencing)
- ICA (Independent Component Analysis for artifact removal)
- ICA+ASR (ICA plus Artifact Subspace Reconstruction).

Table 1: Pre-processing Pipelines considered in [Del Pup et al., 2024](#)

preprocessing step	Raw	Filt	ICA	ICA+ASR
non-EEG channels removal	✓	✓	✓	✓
time segments removal			✓	✓
baseline removal		✓	✓	✓
resampling	✓	✓	✓	✓
filtering		✓	✓	✓
independent component analysis			✓	✓
automatic component rejection			✓	✓
bad-channel removal				✓
bad-time windows correction (ASR)				✓
spherical interpolation				✓
re-reference		✓	✓	✓
template alignment	✓	✓	✓	✓

These pipelines were applied to six open-access EEG datasets representing diverse use cases: physiological (Eye open/closed), motor imagery (MMI), and clinical conditions (Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, First Episode Psychosis, Sleep Deprivation). This selection ensured representation of different noise profiles, subject variability, and biomedical relevance, supporting both task-specific and general conclusions.

For model evaluation, four established EEG deep learning architectures were used: EEGNet, ShallowConvNet, DeepConvNet, and FBCNet, chosen to represent

increasing architectural complexity and different spatial-temporal feature extraction strategies. Each model was trained using a Nested Leave-N-Subjects-Out (N-LNSO) cross-validation scheme — ensuring subject-independent evaluation by iteratively rotating subjects across training, validation, and test folds. This robust evaluation produced a total of 4,800 trained models (4 pipelines × 4 architectures × 6 tasks × 10 outer folds × 5 inner folds).

Performance was assessed using balanced accuracy, preferred for biomedical data due to class imbalance. Statistical significance between pipelines was tested at both the intra-task level (Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm correction) and the inter-task level (Friedman test with Nemenyi post-hoc analysis), yielding a rigorous multi-level comparison of preprocessing effects.

2.1.3 Results

Figure 1: Overview of pre-processing pipeline performance across models, showing how often each approach outperformed the others.

The comparative analysis revealed clear and consistent trends across models and tasks (Figure 1). Models trained on raw data consistently performed worse, confirming that unprocessed EEG lacks sufficient signal quality for deep learning. In contrast, the Filt pipeline, involving only minimal filtering and common average re-referencing, achieved the best overall balance between accuracy, robustness, and computational efficiency, outperforming more complex pipelines in over 50% of all training instances.

While ICA and ICA+ASR occasionally improved results in clinical datasets (e.g., Parkinson’s and Alzheimer’s, where spectral changes are diagnostically informative), they often reduced accuracy in non-clinical tasks such as eye-state and motor imagery classification. This indicates that aggressive artifact removal can suppress task-relevant neural or physiological components.

Statistical testing confirmed significant intra-task differences ($p < 0.001$ in multiple tasks), with Filt consistently yielding the highest median balanced accuracy across all architectures. The Friedman test revealed inter-task significance only for DeepConvNet, suggesting that architecture design modulates sensitivity to preprocessing complexity.

Overall, these findings show that lightweight, standardized preprocessing provides robust and generalizable performance across heterogeneous EEG datasets, enabling scalable EEG harmonization without over-filtering or introducing preprocessing bias.

2.2 Data Partitioning

Data partitioning is critical for developing generalizable deep learning (DL) models for electroencephalography (EEG). A primary challenge is data leakage, where improper splitting of data - such as using segments from the same subject in both training and test sets - allows models to "memorize" subject-specific noise rather than learning general neural patterns. This leads to severely inflated and misleading performance metrics that do not translate to new subjects. To systematically investigate this issue, [Del Pup et al., \(2025\)](#) evaluate how different cross-validation strategies impact model performance in cross-subject EEG analysis. This study directly supports the HEREDITARY project's goal of establishing robust and unbiased frameworks for biomedical data analysis.

2.2.1 Objective

The main objective of this study was to quantify how different cross-validation and data partitioning schemes affect model performance, reliability, and generalizability in EEG deep learning. Specifically, the analysis aimed to identify how leakage between data splits, especially across subjects, inflates accuracy and biases interpretation, and to establish practical methodological guidelines for preventing these issues. By doing so, the work supports the creation of a harmonized EEG evaluation framework, reducing inconsistencies across studies and ensuring that HEREDITARY's multimodal pipelines rely on rigorously validated neural models.

2.2.2 Methods

Five cross-validation strategies were evaluated:

- K-Fold (sample-based)
- Leave-N-Subjects-Out (LNSO)
- Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO)
- Nested-LNSO (N-LNSO)
- Nested-LOSO (N-LOSO)

Figure 2: Overview of cross-validation strategies highlighting how nested subject-based approaches ensure independent training, validation, and test sets to prevent data leakage.

Experiments were performed on three representative EEG classification tasks - Brain-Computer Interface, Parkinson’s disease, and Alzheimer’s disease - spanning both clinical and non-clinical domains. Four deep learning architectures of increasing complexity were evaluated: ShallowConvNet, EEGNet, DeepConvNet, and Temporal-ResNet (T-ResNet). Overall, more than 100,000 models were trained using consistent hyperparameter settings and early stopping protocols, ensuring statistical robustness. Performance was measured using balanced accuracy, chosen to account for class imbalance, and analyzed across architectures to quantify model-specific sensitivity to partitioning strategies.

2.2.3 Results

The study revealed strong and systematic effects of data partitioning on model performance. Sample-based methods (K-Fold) produced artificially high accuracies, with models often exceeding 95–100% balanced accuracy on pathology classification tasks, values later shown to result from data overlap between subjects. These inflated results confirm that sample-level Cross-validation (CV) allows networks to exploit subject-specific signal features rather than condition-related neural patterns.

In contrast, subject-based and nested approaches yielded lower but more realistic and reproducible accuracies, accurately reflecting the challenge of cross-subject generalization. Nested methods (N-LNSO, N-LOSO) completely prevented data leakage by separating validation and test sets, albeit requiring substantially more computational time.

Model-wise, larger architectures such as T-ResNet and DeepConvNet were more sensitive to partitioning errors, exhibiting pronounced overfitting when non-nested methods were used. Simpler architectures, particularly ShallowConvNet, achieved more stable and generalizable results across all CV settings.

Figure 3 illustrates these outcomes, showing a consistent performance drop and higher variance when moving from sample-based to subject-based validation, confirming that nested subject-based CV is essential for reliable EEG-DL evaluation.

Figure 3: Comparison of balanced accuracies showing that subject-based validation produces lower but more reliable performances than sample-based methods across all EEG models.

In summary, these results demonstrate that robust model validation in EEG-DL requires subject-based and ideally nested cross-validation schemes. Despite their computational cost, such approaches ensure methodological integrity, reduce overestimation of model accuracy, and align with HEREDITARY's goal of establishing reproducible pipelines for large-scale biomedical data integration.

2.3 Self-Supervised Learning

In the domain of EEG analysis, self-supervised learning (SSL) methods provide a promising route to extract robust feature embeddings that generalize across subjects, devices, and recording conditions. The [selfEEG](#) library by [Del Pup et al., 2024](#), represents a valuable resource designed specifically to facilitate this objective.

2.3.1 Objective

The main objective of this module is to harmonize EEG recordings obtained with varying protocols and devices, thereby reducing variability not attributable to underlying neural activity. Through the development of standardized preprocessing combined with self-supervised workflows, the project aims to:

- Increase the comparability of heterogeneous EEG datasets.
- Provide embeddings for downstream tasks such as biomarker discovery, patient stratification, and multimodal integration.
- Enhancing data quality and cross-cohort interoperability.

2.3.2 Methods

The methodological workflow is organized into four distinct sub-modules:

1. **Base:** this module contains core data loaders, augmentation utilities, and backbone wrappers common to both pre-training and fine-tuning pipelines.
2. **Contrastive:** here we implement standard contrastive self-supervised algorithms (e.g., [SimCLR](#), [MoCo](#)) which maximize agreement between two views of the same sample while pushing apart different samples.
3. **Predictive:** this module integrates algorithms such as [BYOL](#) and [SimSiam](#) that predict one view's representation from another without explicit negative samples.
4. **Generative:** this component consists of auto-encoder or reconstruction-based pre-training schemes (e.g., [Barlow Twins](#), [VICReg](#)) that learn to generate or decorrelate features and thus obtain invariant embeddings.

The modular design of this workflow allows seamless plugging of different SSL strategies depending on the modality, dataset size, and downstream task requirements. A schematic illustration of SSL and contrastive learning is shown in [Figure 4](#) and [Figure 5](#), respectively.

Figure 4: Scheme of SSL Learning general approach

Figure 5: Scheme of Contrastive learning general approach

In support of this, the library selfEEG provides highly relevant tools:

- It offers modules for data loading and splitting, including subject- and session-based partitioning.
- It implements a wide range of data augmentations tailored to EEG signals (e.g., band-noise addition, channel dropout, permutation, phase swap).
- It contains SSL loss functions and pre-implemented algorithms adaptable to EEG encoders.
- It includes a set of EEG-specific backbone encoders (e.g., EEGNet, DeepConvNet, ResNet1D) that can be plugged into SSL pipelines.
- While it does not offer a full preprocessing stack (e.g., ICA, ASR), it supports basic operations such as filtering and resampling, and works well when combined with specialized EEG-preprocessing frameworks.

By leveraging selfEEG within the HEREDITARY pipeline, the harmonization effort can adopt a well-established open-source toolkit that supports reproducible SSL workflows on EEG

2.3.3 Results

The SelfEEG open-source library is being used by researchers around the world ([Wang et al. 2025](#); [Monachino et al. 2025](#)). The workflow built around this library is currently being applied to extract embeddings from heterogeneous EEG datasets, aiming to support reproducibility and consistent downstream analysis. At this stage, the work is ongoing and serves as a foundation for future validation and integration within the HEREDITARY framework.

3 MRI

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has become one of the most important tools in biomedical research and clinical diagnostics, providing detailed anatomical and functional information without invasive procedures. Despite its advantages, the variability introduced by different scanners, acquisition protocols, and imaging sites poses a significant challenge for large-scale and longitudinal studies. Such differences can lead to heterogeneous data, reducing comparability across studies and potentially obscuring true biological signals ([Roca et al., 2023](#)).

Recent developments in data harmonization have focused on addressing these inconsistencies through deep learning. Cycle-consistent adversarial networks, for example, have been applied to reduce scanner- and site-related effects by standardizing intensity patterns across datasets ([Marzi et al., 2024](#)). Building on this progress ([Beizaee et al., 2025](#)), proposed an unsupervised harmonization approach using normalizing flows. Their framework aligns MR images from different domains without requiring labeled data or access to the original source domain, demonstrating robust generalization in both adult and neonatal brain MRI applications.

In addition to these methods, self-supervised learning has gained traction as a means to enhance harmonization and feature extraction. These approaches can learn meaningful representations directly from unlabeled multimodal data, improving the interpretability and reliability of downstream analyses ([Fedorov et al., 2024](#)).

3.1 Reproducibility in neuroimaging

Reproducibility is the ability to obtain consistent results using the same input data, methods, and computational environment. In neuroimaging deep-learning contexts, achieving reproducibility is particularly challenging due to heterogeneous acquisition equipment, variable preprocessing pipelines, and complex model architectures ([Botvinik-Nezer R et al., 2022](#)).

Toward improving reproducibility in neuroimaging deep learning studies ([Del Pup & Atzori, 2024](#)), discusses the reproducibility crisis affecting neuroimaging-based deep learning and proposes a structured checklist of essential elements to improve transparency and reliability in this research field.

3.1.1 Objective

The study aimed to identify the main causes of poor reproducibility in neuroimaging deep learning studies and to provide clear, actionable guidelines for researchers. It introduced a comprehensive framework of 30 key reproducibility criteria grouped into six categories: software and hardware, dataset, data preprocessing, model architecture, training hyperparameters, and model evaluation. The objective was to ensure that future studies could be replicated under equivalent computational and methodological conditions, thereby increasing scientific trust and comparability across works.

3.1.2 Methods

The authors synthesized findings from existing reviews and reproducibility initiatives in medical imaging, such as those from [Renard et al., \(2020\)](#) and [Moassefi et al., \(2024\)](#), to design a practical reproducibility checklist. Each category was analyzed to define the essential reporting elements—such as software versions, data availability, parameter initialization, and validation schemes—and to specify where these details should be placed (paper, supplementary material, or repository). The approach emphasized the integration of open-source code, standardized data formats and transparent reporting practices to facilitate replication and benchmarking.

3.1.3 Results

The proposed checklist serves as both a methodological guide and a reporting standard for the neuroimaging community. It highlights critical gaps in current practices, such as the fact that only about 10% of neuroscience studies share their source code, compared to 70% in computer vision. The framework provides concrete recommendations to mitigate these deficiencies and improve reproducibility throughout the research lifecycle, from data collection to evaluation. Ultimately, the study concludes that reproducibility must be prioritized as a central scientific requirement, ensuring that deep learning advances in neuroimaging are robust, transparent, and clinically meaningful.

4 Clinical data

Clinical data harmonization is a prerequisite for robust biomedical research, addressing the non-biological heterogeneity inherent in multicenter datasets. As multimodal datasets expand, differences in measurement scales, protocols, and batch effects can obscure true biological signals ([Magateshvaren Saras et al., 2025](#)). Effective integration also requires representation strategies that respect variable types, including continuous, categorical, and ordinal data ([Yang et al., 2025](#)). Addressing these challenges in the context of ordinal clinical measures, the following work presents an unsupervised phenotyping framework. By leveraging the General Distance Measure (GDM) to handle scale heterogeneity, this study identifies stable, data-driven patient subgroups in stroke cohorts, bridging the gap between behavioral symptoms and neuroanatomical lesion patterns without relying on predefined labels.

4.1 Unsupervised Clinical Phenotyping

Unsupervised learning techniques are increasingly used to identify clinically meaningful patient subgroups from heterogeneous biomedical data, without relying on predefined labels. These methods help uncover latent patterns in symptoms, imaging, or genetic data, facilitating syndrome discovery and personalized treatment strategies. For example, [Tshimanga et al., \(2025\)](#) applied an unsupervised clustering framework to stratify ischemic stroke patients based solely on behavioral symptom profiles from NIHSS scores, revealing subgroups with distinct lesion patterns and validating known neurological syndromes through a purely data-driven approach.

4.1.2 Objective

The objective of this study was to develop and apply an unsupervised framework to identify behaviorally coherent subgroups of stroke patients using NIHSS scores and to

map each subgroup to characteristic lesion distributions. The approach aimed to overcome limitations of traditional methods—such as treating ordinal data as continuous or using linear models—by incorporating a similarity measure tailored to ordinal clinical data and enabling robust, data-driven phenotyping.

4.1.2 Methods

We introduced a workflow using the General Distance Measure (GDM) to compute patient similarity based on ordinal NIHSS scores. A similarity network was constructed and partitioned using Repeated Spectral Clustering (RSC), a consensus method that enhances stability through evidence accumulation. Finally, voxel-wise lesion analysis was performed to identify neuroanatomical signatures significantly associated with each behavioral cluster. Because GDM is designed to compare samples even when variables follow different scales, ranges, or statistical distributions, it can also be applied to a wide variety of tabular clinical datasets where heterogeneity in feature types is common.

4.1.3 Results

The unsupervised framework successfully identified five clinically coherent behavioral clusters from NIHSS scores, each linked to distinct lesion patterns. *Figure 6* visualizes the patient similarity network based on the clustering co-occurrence matrix, where nodes represent patients and darker red connections indicate patients frequently grouped. This demonstrates a stable, data-driven partition of the cohort into distinct phenotypic subgroups. Importantly, this approach is generalizable and is already being applied to other clinical variables and disease contexts — including conditions such as Parkinson’s disease, ALS, and psychiatric disorders — where uncovering latent patient subtypes is equally valuable for precision medicine.

Figure 6: Patient similarity network visualizing the five stable behavioral clusters.

Figure 7 provides a detailed characterization of each cluster, combining radar charts of NIHSS symptom profiles with corresponding lesion heatmaps. The radar charts show the minimum, median, and maximum scores for each deficit, revealing specific syndrome patterns (e.g., left/right motor deficits, language impairment). The heatmaps display the collective lesion distribution for each cluster, with brighter colors indicating voxels lesioned in more subjects. This integrated view confirms that the purely behavioral clusters exhibit anatomically specific lesion correlates, such as corticospinal tract involvement in motor deficits and temporal-parietal regions in language deficits, validating the method's ability to uncover biologically meaningful subtypes from heterogeneous clinical data.

Figure 7: Radar charts of NIHSS symptom profiles and corresponding lesion heat maps for each cluster.

5 Optical Coherence Tomography

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) faces significant challenges in multi-site studies due to technical variations between different scanning devices and acquisition protocols. These differences create systematic biases, or batch effects, that can compromise the reliability of quantitative analyses and hinder the generalizability of deep learning models ([Chen et al., 2023](#)).

In the context of neurodegenerative disease, retinal ophthalmology leverages multimodal imaging and artificial intelligence to detect early pathological changes, offering a non-invasive window into brain health. For instance, the integration of OCT and AI can identify retinal nerve fiber layer thinning and other ocular biomarkers associated with Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, enabling potential early intervention ([Suh et al. 2023](#)).

Within the HEREDITARY project, one recent study focused on OCT data. The work explored publicly available OCT datasets to assess their potential for harmonization and integration into large-scale federated learning frameworks aimed at biomedical data analysis ([Rozhyna et al., 2024](#)). Moreover, ongoing work is investigating SSL approaches for OCT images within federated settings, aiming to enhance cross-site generalization while preserving data privacy.

5.1.1 Objective

The main objective was to systematically identify, analyze, and validate publicly accessible OCT datasets for retinal imaging. The study aimed to determine their quality, representativeness, and compatibility with harmonization and federated learning approaches. By assessing dataset completeness, diversity, and acquisition variability, the work sought to establish a foundation for developing interoperable deep learning frameworks capable of generalizing across centers and devices.

5.1.2 Methods

A systematic review of publicly available OCT datasets was conducted using online repositories such as Mendeley, Zenodo, PubMed, and Google Dataset Search. Each dataset was examined for accessibility, imaging modality, disease coverage, data format, and annotation quality. Information about acquisition instruments, image resolution, and metadata was also collected to assess standardization levels. Comparative analysis was carried out to evaluate dataset overlap and potential for harmonized model training.

5.1.3 Results

The study identified 23 open-access OCT datasets covering various retinal conditions. Results showed considerable heterogeneity in acquisition devices, image formats, and metadata detail, with the Heidelberg Spectralis system being the most frequently used. Around one quarter of datasets included information on eye laterality, while most lacked standardized clinical labels. *Figure 8* illustrates the distribution of diseases across these datasets, revealing substantial imbalance and heterogeneity that represent key sources of variability. Despite this variability, several datasets demonstrated sufficient consistency and annotation quality to be used in federated deep learning pipelines.

These findings emphasize the importance of harmonization efforts to enable robust, scalable, and interoperable OCT-based models for biomedical research.

Figure 8: Disease representation across the different datasets considered in (Rozhyna et al., 2024)

6 Multi-omics

The integration of multi-omics data is critical for constructing a unified model of cellular function and disease pathogenesis. However, this integration is significantly challenged by technical and biological variability.

A primary technical obstacle is the batch effect, where non-biological variations introduced by different instruments, reagents, or processing batches create systematic biases that can obscure true biological signals and compromise the reproducibility of findings ([Leek et al., 2010](#)). Harmonization methods are therefore essential to align disparate datasets, removing these technical confounders to enable valid comparative and integrative analyses ([Nygaard et al., 2016](#)).

Beyond technical noise, a fundamental source of biological variation is the difference between cell types. Bulk omics measurements from tissue samples average signals across diverse cellular populations, masking critical cell-type-specific molecular events ([Lähnemann et al., 2020](#)). Effective multi-omics analysis must therefore employ strategies that not only correct for batch effects but also preserve and resolve these biologically meaningful differences across cell types.

Within the HEREDITARY project, research on molecular data focuses on harmonizing heterogeneous omics datasets to enable robust multimodal integration and

downstream biological discovery. One of our recent studies, *An Overview of Self-Supervised Deep Learning Applications to Molecular data* (submitted in Briefings in Bioinformatics), reviewed emerging self-supervised learning (SSL) approaches for molecular sequence analysis, aiming to understand how large-scale unlabeled data can be leveraged to extract biological representations.

6.1.1 Objective

The main objective of this work was to provide a comprehensive overview of self-supervised deep learning methods applied to molecular data, including genomic, transcriptomic, single-cell, and proteomic datasets. The study sought to summarize SSL paradigms, identify key applications in omics, and evaluate their potential for integrating large-scale molecular data without relying on extensive labeling. By analyzing the most relevant studies and available open-source resources, the goal was to guide future developments in SSL-based biological modeling.

6.1.2 Methods

A systematic review was conducted using major repositories such as PubMed, arXiv, bioRxiv, and Google Scholar. Keywords related to “self-supervised learning,” “genomics,” “molecular data,” and “transformer-based models” were used to identify relevant works. Seventeen studies were selected based on their explicit application of SSL to omics. Each was analyzed for model architecture, pretext task (e.g., masked language modeling, contrastive learning), data modality, tokenization strategy, and availability of reproducible code. Applications were grouped by data type, covering DNA, RNA, single-cell, and protein-level data.

6.1.3 Results

The review identified key SSL approaches such as DNABERT-2, Nucleotide Transformer, Hyena-DNA, and Evo2 as major advances in molecular sequence modeling. These models demonstrated the ability to capture long-range dependencies and biological motifs directly from unlabeled data, improving performance in downstream tasks like promoter prediction, transcription factor binding, and splice site detection. SSL was shown to enhance generalization and reduce reliance on labeled datasets, particularly in genomics and transcriptomics. The study concluded that SSL represents a promising approach for harmonizing large-scale omics data, supporting the development of integrative and federated learning strategies in biomedical research.

Conclusion

This report underscores that harmonization and methodological rigor are fundamental to advancing reliable multimodal deep learning in biomedicine. Within the neurophysiological domain, we demonstrated how complementary strategies — encompassing preprocessing optimization, robust data partitioning, and self-supervised representation learning — collectively enhance the robustness, generalization, and interpretability of EEG-based models. These findings highlight the necessity of harmonized analytical pipelines to ensure reproducible and scalable neurophysiological research.

In the neuroimaging and behavioral domain, unsupervised clustering of NIHSS scores revealed stable and biologically meaningful subgroups of stroke patients, emphasizing how harmonized data and unbiased analytical workflows can drive interpretable phenotype discovery. Similarly, the application of harmonization and reproducibility principles across imaging modalities such as MRI and OCT reinforced their essential role in achieving cross-site comparability and trustworthy clinical translation.

Parallel efforts in molecular data analysis, including a comprehensive review of self-supervised deep learning applications to genomics and other omics, aim to establish scalable methodologies capable of compressing and integrating biologically relevant information from large unlabeled datasets. These developments pave the way for harmonized, data-efficient, and interpretable modeling across molecular and imaging domains.

Collectively, the studies presented here converge toward a unified vision: harmonization, reproducibility, and self-supervised learning are not isolated technical objectives but interdependent pillars of trustworthy multimodal biomedical AI. Within the HEREDITARY project, these principles form the foundation for building integrative, reproducible, and privacy-preserving analytical frameworks capable of advancing precision medicine and scientific transparency.

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